

Quality 3-year Fast-Track PhD Student Crib Sheet

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1. Thesis length 70,000 words plus references
2. Problem-based research - avoid exploratory, single-question and hypothesis testing
3. Value of PhD knowledge outcomes more than \$500,000
4. Use 3 year PhD time plan
5. *Exactly* specify research in candidacy, especially in ethics.
6. Use Endnote – use APA style sheet
7. Aim for ‘PASS with minor amendments’
8. Write in thesis during candidacy every week from week 1
9. Use Perry/Love 5 chapter thesis model
10. Plan PhD with weekly timeline.
11. Ensure ZERO lost time due to your administration
12. Ensure ZERO lost time from administration by supervisor and university systems
13. Align your PhD process exactly with university assessment and administration process dates
14. Meet with supervisor weekly
15. Arrange with supervisor to keep you on your weekly timeline
16. Ensure supervisor proofreads and corrects your writing each week
17. Supervisor to identify maximum 3 new improvements to candidate's writing each week
18. Candidates address each improvement in the next week's writing
19. Create one refereed conference paper
20. Work 4-5 hours on your PhD *every* day.
21. Take 4 weeks holiday per year – no more and no less
22. Use a Doctoral skills development matrix

Published by Praxis Education 2011